

D6.1. Project logo and website

Project full title	Guest XR: A Machine Learning Agent for Social Harmony in eXtended Reality
Project Acronym:	GuestXR
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Leader of this deliverable:	EUT
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Deliverable Information Sheet

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Executive summary

This deliverable reports on the development of GuestXR Visual Corporate Image (VCI) and project webpage. The document includes the project's logo, Word templates for project activities, a Power Point template for presentations and a visual identity standards guidebook defining and outlining how to use identifying elements pertaining to the project, such as logos, colours, fonts and graphic elements.

In addition, this deliverable also describes how the GuestXR's project webpage has been created, summarising the structure, the content and website functionalities.

Table of contents

Deliverable Information Sheet.....	2
Executive summary.....	2
Table of contents.....	3
List of figures.....	4
List of tables.....	4
List of abbreviations.....	5
1. Project branding and templates.....	6
1.1 Logo.....	6
1.1.1 Use of the logo.....	7
1.2 Visual Corporate Identity (VCI) manual.....	7
1.1.2 Corporate colours.....	8
1.1.3 Fonts.....	8
1.1.4 Stationery.....	9
1.1.5 Graphic resources.....	10
1.3 Templates.....	11
1.3.1 Power point presentation.....	11
1.3.2 Deliverable template.....	12
1.3.3 Agenda template.....	13
1.3.4 Minutes template.....	14
1.3.5 Letter template.....	14
2 Project website.....	16
2.1.1 Structure.....	16
2.1.2 Content.....	17
2.1.3 Imagery.....	36
2.1.4 Header and footer layout.....	37
2.1.5 Management and updating policy.....	38
2.1.6 Analytics.....	38
2.1.7 Site hosting, installation and maintenance.....	38
2.1.8 Data protection.....	38
2.1.9 Website KPIs.....	39
3 ANNEXES.....	40
3.1 Website privacy policy.....	40
3.2 Website legal warning.....	43
3.3 Website cookies policy.....	46
3.4 Community of interest privacy policy.....	51
3.5 Contact form privacy policy.....	52
3.6 User group privacy policy.....	52

List of figures

Figure 1: Full-colour GuestXR logo	6
Figure 2. Full-colour logo for white backgrounds	6
Figure 3. Black & white logo	6
Figure 4. GuestXR logo proposals	7
Figure 5. Logo adaptation in a background with an image	7
Figure 6. GuestXR colour palette	8
Figure 7. Fonts for promotional and communication issues.....	9
Figure 8. Fonts for deliverables and other internal documents	9
Figure 9. GuestXR stationery	10
Figure 10. Graphic resources to be used for designing GuestXR's materials.....	10
Figure 11. GuestXR's Twitter header	11
Figure 12. Slides of GuestXR PowerPoint presentation template.....	11
Figure 13. View of some pages of the deliverable template	13
Figure 14. GuestXR agenda template.....	13
Figure 15. GuestXR template for meeting minutes	14
Figure 16. GuestXR letter template.....	15
Figure 17: Project website at M2.....	16
Figure 18: Planned website structure by the end of the project	17
Figure 19: GuestXR slider and menu.....	18
Figure 20: View of GuestXR homepage contents https://guestxr.eu/	21
Figure 21: View of the about page https://guestxr.eu/about-guestxr/	25
Figure 22: View of consortium page https://guestxr.eu/consortium/	30
Figure 23: Example of partners' page	31
Figure 24: GuestXR website use cases page - https://guestxr.eu/use-cases/	32
Figure 25. View of GuestXR user group page - https://guestxr.eu/user-group/	33
Figure 26. View of GuestXR news & events page - https://guestxr.eu/news-events/	34
Figure 27. View of GuestXR resources page	35
Figure 28. View of GuestXR contact page	36
Figure 29: Header and footer layout	37
Figure 30: GuestXR footer	37
Figure 31: GuestXR header	37
Figure 32: View of Matomo dashboard	38

List of tables

Table 1: Website KPIs.....	39
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List of abbreviations

AR	Augmented reality
D	Deliverable
EU	European Union
ML	Machine Learning
MR	Mixed reality
RL	Reinforcing Learning
T	Task
VCI	Visual Corporate Identity
VR	Virtual Reality
WP	Work Package
XR	Extended Reality

1. Project branding and templates

According to the work plan, Eurecat is responsible for designing GuestXR official Visual Corporate Image (VCI), aimed at properly aligning all communication and dissemination materials across all the tasks of the project.

The Visual Corporate Image is crucial to create and establish GuestXR's identity, as well as to give a coherent and consistent image of the project. It is also important to use the elements established in the VCI manual properly and only employ the authorised documents templates in order to convey the properties and goals of the project as a brand and do it consistently.

1.1 Logo

The logo is the main brand element of the visual identity of GuestXR and has the purpose to represent the different concepts surrounding the project.

As pictured in Figure 1, GuestXR's logo is framed in a black screen where we can find here an X formed by 4 different layers of "realities" (MR, VR, AR & AMB) interacting in this virtual space (the black screen).

Figure 1: Full-colour GuestXR logo

Depending on its application, different versions of the logo have been developed, including a full colour logo with the name of the project in black and the surrounding figure in white (Figure 2) to use when applied in front of a colour background, and a white & black-black version (Figure 3) to be shown whenever the full colour logo cannot be used.

Figure 2. Full-colour logo for white backgrounds

Figure 3. Black & white logo

Other set of logos was considered by all partners in an election process before finally choosing the final one.

Figure 4. GuestXR logo proposals

1.1.1 Use of the logo

Several examples on how to use the logo are included in the visual corporate identity manual in order to guide partners during its application in project materials.

Figure 5. Logo adaptation in a background with an image

1.2 Visual Corporate Identity (VCI) manual

A visual identity and standards manual has been created and distributed among all partners to ensure that project's branding is not compromised, and all partners are capable to use the elements properly with the objective to convey the properties and goals of the GuestXR project as a brand.

The visual identity guidelines define and outline how to use identifying elements pertaining to the project, including logos, fonts, colours, stationery and graphic resources. Additionally, it sets a design layout for project promotional materials to be developed in the next months. Partners should treat and use this manual as a source of the materials and instructions and as a basis for further development of project materials.

The sections hereinafter include and describe some parts designed in the manual:

1.1.2 Corporate colours

This section presents the project’s colour palette that must be used in all project’s materials, such as the website, social media and other promotional and graphic elements.

According to the palette designed, the corporate colours of GuestXR are Bright Blue (#2961ff), Black (#000000), Turquoise (#03ebcf), Navy Blue (#05478c), Sky Blue (#00a3e3), Purple (#9900e8), Red (#ff145c), Orange (#ff8514) and Ocher (#bfab00).

Figure 6. GuestXR colour palette

Out of the project palette, two main colours have been given preference in materials applications and will be used as main brand colours for GuestXR project: the Navy Blue (#05478c) and the Red (#ff145c) colour.

1.1.3 Fonts

The VCI manual also establishes three types of fonts to be used for project documents and materials.

“POPPINS BOLD” will be the special font used for titles of promotional and advertising materials. This type of font and its different versions are free, and partners can download it from Google Fonts from [here](#).

As the manual establishes, the text font for promotional and communication items will be “Roboto”, which can be also downloaded in Google Fonts Page for free [here](#).

Figure 7. Fonts for promotional and communication issues

On the other hand, “Arial” is the main font established for deliverables and internal documents because it is a standard Microsoft Office font included in Word and Power Point documents, among some others.

Figure 8. Fonts for deliverables and other internal documents

1.1.4 Stationery

The Visual Corporative Identity manual designed for GuestXR project also includes different elements designed for stationery materials, such as letters, envelopes and business cards, as well as a proposal of the application of the project logo in digital supports.

Figure 9. GuestXR stationery

1.1.5 Graphic resources

This section shows the graphic items which can be used for the design of promotional materials, externals and internal project presentations or other documents. These elements have been broadly used for the design of the project's Word and Power Point templates, as well as headers for the project's Twitter account.

Figure 10. Graphic resources to be used for designing GuestXR's materials

Figure 11. GuestXR's Twitter header

1.3 Templates

Eurecat has prepared different templates, which have been already shared with all partners. A Power Point template has been created for internal and external presentations, as well as three different Word documents: one for deliverables, one for meetings' agenda and other purposes and another one to be used for meetings' minutes.

These template materials must be used throughout all project's execution in order to maintain a coherent and consistent image.

1.3.1 Power point presentation

A Power Point template has been designed to be used for all GuestXR project's internal and external presentations.

This document includes a variety of slides with different options to include the text, and different visual elements and to be used and adapted by all partners when preparing an internal or external project's presentation. Two front cover proposals have been prepared, one with an image of a woman wearing a VR headset and a simpler design making use of GuestXR graphic resources.

A screenshot of some slides is shown below:

Figure 12. Slides of GuestXR PowerPoint presentation template

1.3.2 Deliverable template

A Word document template has been produced and shared with all the consortium partners to be used for all project's deliverables.

This template establishes the use of a page header with the project's logo and the funding body's logo and a footer with some information about the document and a graphic element created for project materials.

Aspects related the fonts used, size, tables, figures, ordered and unordered lists, references, footnotes, etc. are defined in the template.

Normal Text is Arial 11pt, single line spacing and justified.

Every section has to start at a new page.

Title 1 is the Section Heading.

Titles (2-5) are the Numbered Subsections* (examples in page 9).

Template for unordered lists:

- Style bulleted – To be used with bullets (unordered lists). Don't change the bullets unless absolutely necessary
 - Style bulleted – 2nd Level of bullets
 - Style bulleted – 3rd Level of bullets

It's important to have a template for ordered lists too:

1. The style is called Style Numbered and it follows the same rules as the unordered list.
 - i. The 2nd Level of the ordered list uses Latin numbering.
 - a. The 3rd Level of the ordered list uses the alphabet.

If using an excerpt from a book or a scientific article it is proper to place it in indentation using style Excerpt as follows:

This paragraph report directly another's words. As you can see there is indentation of 1,2cm from left and right while there are spaces of 8pt. from the previous and from the next paragraph. The font is Arial, 10pt.

[1] References are marked using a numbered list style referred to as References. This style has the following specifications: Arial, 10pt, single line spacing, 6pt. space from the previous paragraph.

Figure 13. View of some pages of the deliverable template

1.3.3 Agenda template

The template designed for meetings' agenda presents a header page with the GuestXR and funding body's logo and a footer with some information of the project. The font used for title agenda's document is Arial 16pt Bold and in the main project corporate colour and for the normal text is also Arial 10,5pt, single line spacing and justified.

A screenshot of the template is shown below:

Figure 14. GuestXR agenda template

1.3.4 Minutes template

This template will be used for taking minutes of project meetings and recording the list of attendants. This document also includes a header page with the GuestXR logo and reference to the EU funding and a footer with some information.

For the main title of the document Arial 16pt Bold is used in the main project corporate colour, while for subsections headings the font used is Arial 14pt and for normal text Arial 11pt.

Figure 15. GuestXR template for meeting minutes

1.3.5 Letter template

This template is specifically designed for letters that consortium partners may need to write during the project. It includes some lines for the details of the sender and reference to GuestXR project. Text is Arial 11pt.

Figure 16. GuestXR letter template

2 Project website

According to the work plan, Eurecat has been responsible for designing and implementing the official GuestXR project website and launching it on M2 (February 2022). The registered URL is www.questxr.eu.

The sections hereinafter describe the web platform. **The website will be the anchor for all communication and dissemination activities related to the project and will serve as a central point of entry for all public material**, including the project's basic information, activities and events. The website will be continuously updated with news, links to other relevant sites, details of published papers, conferences and exhibitions during the project and will remain active at least three years after the project's finalisation to serve as information of reference on fracture toughness.

The website platform follows the corporate visual identity of the project and it gives access to the GuestXR social media channels (Twitter and YouTube).

Considering that different authors might update the site, a Content Management System (CMS) has been adopted, to easily and quickly publish the content. Eurecat has proposed to use WordPress, as the Eurecat's Research Communications Office has wide experience with this CMS.

The website is optimised for browsing on tablets and smartphones, so the website has been developed using a responsive design approach.

2.1.1 Structure

The following information architecture for GuestXR website is proposed in the figure below. In blue you can see the pages /structure that have been created for the website launch, while, in red, the proposed structure that will be developed afterwards, in line with project advances.

Further changes to the website structure may be made in the future to allocate documents and dissemination actions, as well as to support specific WP or tasks.

Figure 17: Project website at M2

Figure 18: Planned website structure by the end of the project

2.1.2 Content

The texts hereinafter describe the contents published on the first version of the website.

2.1.2.1 Homepage

It includes one slider: “Developing a machine learning agent for social harmony in Extended Reality”.

The homepage also includes a short description of the project and its main objectives/activities planned. In addition, a section mentioning the consortium linking to the partners’ page has been designed and included in the homepage.

As soon as the “News & Events” sections have some new articles and contents, a section at the homepage showing the latest publications, together with the project’s Twitter feed will be created. Specific sections will be created to promote and divulge specific results, such as the “The Guest” or the project use cases.

Figure 19: GuestXR slider and menu

GuestXR in a nutshell

Creating a new machine learning agent addressing conflicts and unlocking interaction in extended reality environments

About the project

The GuestXR project aims to create an immersive online social space through extended reality, where the focus is on the existence of a machine learning agent called “The Guest”, which can facilitate interaction between participants to help them achieve their intended goals.

The innovation seeks to help avert conflicts and cyberbullying in digital interaction environments, make it easier for people with communication problems to get involved and detect antisocial behaviour, among other similar issues.

BUTTON – FIND OUT MORE – Link to “About the project”

The Guest

A machine learning agent called “The Guest” is to be created to analyse the individual and social behaviour of the participants based on existing theoretical models from the point of view of neuroscience and social psychology.

“The Guest” will be trained to facilitate different types of social interaction, including situations that may involve conflict, with participants with hearing impairments or that involve changing attitudes towards controversial topics.

BUTTON - ABOUT THE GUEST – Link to “About the project”

“Every gathering of people in virtual and augmented reality has a purpose – either an explicit one - such as to reach an agreement on a topic of discussion, or an implicit one, such as enjoyment. The fundamental idea of The Guest is to help the group of people realise this purpose. This involves exciting research with a strong interdisciplinary component, breaking new ground, and hopefully contributing to the success of social Virtual and Augmented Reality”.

Mel Slater – GuestXR Scientific Coordinator

Use cases

Validation in four proof-of-concept interactive multisensory Extended Reality applications

[BUTTON – FIND OUT MORE](#) – Link to use cases page

Make participants aware

Virtual game to change users’ attitudes and behaviour towards polemic topics such as climate change.

Conflict resolution

Validation of The Guest in geopolitical conflict resolution in conjunction with the United Nations.

Hearing loss

Social inclusivity application to improve communication between hearing-impaired and healthy individuals in XR.

Innovative experiments

Use case selected from two public Open Calls, considering proposals for the facilitation of new VR experiences, inclusivity, and promoting learning and creativity.

Stay in touch!

Subscribe to our newsletter to be informed about the latest news and developments of GuestXR

Subscribe now!

[+ LINK NEWSLETTER SIGN UP FORM](#)

News & events

Latest GuestXR updates!

- [LIST OF NEWS PUBLISHED](#)
- [TWITTER WIDGET](#)

Open call

Two open calls to develop other innovative use cases to check the GuestXR system’s effectiveness will be launched in the second semester of 2023.

- **Artistic residencies**
- **Call for projects**

More information coming soon!

GuestXR partners

A consortium of 8 partners from 6 different European countries works together to ensure social harmony in Virtual and Augmented Reality environments. (Inclusion of project logos)

GUESTXR IN A NUTSHELL

Creating a new machine learning agent addressing conflicts and unlocking interaction in extended reality environments

About the project

The GuestXR project aims to create an immersive online social space through extended reality, where the focus is on the existence of a machine learning agent called "The Guest", which can facilitate interaction between participants to help them achieve their intended goals.

The innovation seeks to help avert conflicts and cyberbullying in digital interaction environments, make it easier for people with communication problems to get involved and detect antisocial behaviour, among other similar issues.

[Find out more](#)

The Guest

A machine learning agent called "The Guest" is to be created to analyse the individual and social behaviour of the participants based on existing theoretical models from the point of view of neuroscience and social psychology.

"The Guest" will be trained to facilitate different types of social interaction, including situations that may involve conflict, with participants with hearing impairments or that involve changing attitudes towards controversial topics.

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Every gathering of people in virtual and augmented reality has a purpose – either an explicit one – such as to reach an agreement on a topic of discussion, or an implicit one, such as enjoyment. The fundamental idea of The Guest is to help the group of people realise this purpose. This involves exciting research with a strong interdisciplinary component, breaking new ground, and hopefully contributing to the success of social Virtual and Augmented Reality

Mel Slater – GuestXR Scientific Coordinator

USE CASES

Validation in four proof-of-concept interactive multisensory Extended Reality applications

[About GuestXR use cases](#)

Make participants aware

Virtual game to change users' attitudes and behaviour towards topics such as climate change.

Conflict resolution

Validation of The Guest in geopolitical conflict resolution in conjunction with other organisations like the United Nations.

Hearing loss

Social inclusivity application to improve communication between hearing-impaired and healthy individuals in XR.

Innovative experiments

Use case selected from two public Open Calls, considering proposals for the facilitation of new VR experiences, inclusivity, and promoting learning and creativity.

Stay in touch!

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Subscribe now!

NEWS & EVENTS

Latest GuestXR updates!

Adapting VR environment into 3D restaurant for a newspaper interview
February 22, 2022
[Read more](#)

Learning Agent harmony in reality
GuestXR project kicks-off!
January 27, 2022
[Read more](#)

Tweets by @GuestXR

- GuestXR Retweeted
Mel Slater @melslater
I would like to thank @PicolInteractive for their fantastic help in supporting our @ERC_Research project #MoTIVE and the Horizon Europe project @GuestXR 1
<https://twitter.com/melslater/status/1492842954796449795>
Feb 22, 2022
- GuestXR Retweeted
TRACCIÓN @TRACCIÓN_EU
Can #accessibility be applied in #VirtualReality? @TransmediaCat are using #EyeTracking technology to understand how to best position #audiences in #immersive environments.
Embed [View on Twitter](#)

OPEN CALLS

Two Open Calls to prove GuestXR system effectiveness

Call to develop other innovative use cases with GuestXR system to be launched in the second semester of 2023.

- Artistic residencies
- Call for new use cases

PROJECT CONSORTIUM

GuestXR Partners

A consortium of 8 partners from 6 different European countries works together to ensure social harmony in Virtual and Augmented Reality environments

[About the consortium](#)

Figure 20: View of GuestXR homepage contents <https://guestxr.eu/>

2.1.2.2 About GuestXR

About the project

The GuestXR project is to develop an immersive virtual social space anchored in extended reality based on examining individual and group behaviour by drawing on existing theoretical models from the neuroscience and social psychology standpoint.

GuestXR solution will feature a machine learning agent designed to unlock interactions between participants and help them achieve their goals, whilst helping users address conflicts in virtual environments.

The project technology will be developed under the “Ethics by Design” approach. This entails considering any potential ethical issues which may come up when using Artificial Intelligence such as respect for human autonomy, prevention of harm, fairness and explicability.

Start-end date: 1 January 2022 – 31 December 2025

Duration: 48 months

Funded under: Horizon 2020 programme H2020-FETPROACT-2020-2

Overall budget: 4.499.519,76 €

Reference number: 101017884

Our vision

“Our vision is to develop a socially interactive multisensory platform system that uses extended reality, virtual and augmented reality, as the medium to bring people together for immersive, synchronous face-to-face interaction with positive social outcomes”

Project phases

From an idea to demonstrating the technology in relevant environment

1. **Development of the Machine Learning Agent:** Application of deep Reinforcement Learning (RL) novel methods to train The Guest to obtain social intelligence, so that it can take specific actions that foster pro-social behaviour and social goals, in the context of Extended Reality applications incorporating ethics-by-design methodology.
2. **Social and affective modelling:** Definition of agent psychological rules of behaviour, development of social behavioural simulations and computational description of body posture and movement features, as well as investigate how individuals’ expressions affect social interaction dynamics.
3. **Integration into experimental studies:** Creation of the overall architecture of the AR and VR systems and development of the multiple representations of The Guest and its actions, as well as self-representation through embodiment in AR and of remote participants.
4. **Multisensory displays:** Investigate and develop multimodal rendering such as haptics and research on multisensory integration and provide setups and guidelines for the project use cases.
5. **Use cases development:** System validation through different use cases, including conflict situations or involving participants with communication problems.

The Guest

Helping people achieve their meeting goals

“The Guest” is a machine learning system to be devised as an agent that can examine participants’ individual and group behaviour by drawing on existing theoretical models from the neuroscience and social psychology standpoint.

The Guest will be able to perform a range of multisensory actions, using, for instance, visual or auditory features to create particular states of mind and stimulate a relaxed environment when it identifies a conflict amongst participants. This combination of AI with immersive systems, virtual and augmented reality will be a hugely challenging research task, given the vagaries of social meetings and individual behaviour.

The Guest may introduce a small obstacle, the overcoming of which requires the cooperation of all participants, provide an opportunity for a relaxing common activity, change the background music to a more soothing one, disrupt escalating interactions by increasing the physical distance or introducing a physical separation between participants (changing the environment) and engage each participant in positive interaction with a dedicated actor.

Research beyond the state of the art

Ground-breaking research and development leading to novel social interactive systems mediated by a Machine Learning agent

- 1) **Machine intelligence:** Reinforcing Learning and algorithms. to start testing The Guest in simulations, and then gradually transfer the agent to increasingly complex social scenarios with real humans, both in AR and VR.
- 2) **Social rules processes:** computational simulations involving ABMs to allow pre-training, testing and adjustment of social rules that will define how to influence social interactions through GuestXR.
- 3) **Real-time know communication:** development of an automatic decoding system for emotions’ recognition from whole-body expressions in realistic situations based on computational movement feature analysis in combination with brain and body measures.
- 4) **Goal-driven socially shared VR and AR:** The research will focus on how the interaction between people in VR and AR environments can be positively enhanced. This will represent a first-time major proof of concept that a Machine Learning system can positively enhance virtual meetings.
- 5) **Multisensorial integration:** establishment of new kinds of human-to-human haptic communication and exploration of haptic devices that deliver tactile sensory inputs through wearables and actuators to create enhanced sensing.

Interested?

Keep up to date on GuestXR developments by subscribing to our newsletter

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ABOUT GUESTXR PROJECT

Creating a new machine learning agent addressing conflicts and unlocking interaction in extended reality environments

The **GuestXR** project objective is to **develop an immersive virtual social space anchored in extended reality** based on examining individual and group behaviour by drawing on existing theoretical models from the **neuroscience and social psychology standpoint**.

GuestXR solution will feature a **machine learning agent designed to unlock interactions between participants** and help them achieve their goals, whilst **helping users address conflicts in virtual environments**.

The project technology will be developed under the **"Ethics by Design" approach**. This entails considering any potential ethical issues which may come up when using Artificial Intelligence such as respect for human autonomy, prevention of harm, fairness and explicability.

Key data

- ✓ **Start-end date:** 1 January 2022 – 31 December 2025
- ✓ **Duration:** 46 months
- ✓ **Funded under** Horizon 2020 programme H2020-FETPROACT-2020-2
- ✓ **Overall budget:** 4.499.519,76 €
- ✓ **Reference number:** 101017884

OUR VISION

Our vision is to develop a socially interactive multisensory platform system that uses extended reality, virtual and augmented reality, as the medium to bring people together for immersive, synchronous face-to-face interaction with positive social outcomes

PROJECT PHASES

From an idea to demonstrating the technology in relevant environment

1

Development of the Machine Learning Agent

Application of deep Reinforcement Learning (RL) novel methods to train The Guest to obtain social intelligence, so that it can take specific actions that foster pro-social behaviour and social goals, in the context of Extended Reality applications incorporating ethics-by-design methodology.

2.

Social and affective modelling

Definition of agent psychological roles of behaviour, development of social behavioural simulations and computational description of body posture and movement features, as well as investigate how individuals' expressions affect social interaction dynamics.

3

Integration into experimental studies

Creation of the overall architecture of the AR and VR systems and development of the multiple representations of The Guest and its actions, as well as self-representation through embodiment in AR and of remote participants.

4.

Multisensory displays

Investigate and develop multimodal rendering such as haptics and research on multisensory integration and provide setups and guidelines for the project use cases.

5

Use cases development

System validation through different use cases, including conflict situations or involving participants with communication problems.

THE GUEST

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RESEARCH BEYOND THE STATE OF THE ART

Ground-breaking research and development leading to novel social interactive systems mediated by a Machine Learning agent

Machine intelligence

Reinforcing Learning and algorithms, to start testing The Guest in simulations, and then gradually transfer the agent to increasingly complex social scenarios with real humans, both in AR and VR.

Social rules processes

Computational simulations involving ABMs to allow pre-training, testing and adjustment of social rules that will define how to influence social interactions through GuestXR.

Real-time communication

Development of an automatic decoding system for emotions' recognition from whole-body expressions in realistic situations based on computational movement feature analysis in combination with brain and body measures.

Goal-driven socially shared VR and AR

The research will focus on how the interaction between people in VR and AR environments can be positively enhanced. This will represent a first-time major proof of concept that a Machine Learning system can positively enhance virtual meetings.

Multisensorial integration

Establishment of new kinds of human-to-human haptic communication and exploration of haptic devices that deliver tactile sensory inputs through wearables and actuators to create enhanced

Interested?

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Figure 21: View of the about page <https://questxr.eu/about-questxr/>

2.1.2.3 Consortium

This page provides information of the entities forming GuestXR consortium and gives access to partners' pages with each partner information and a short explanation on what they will be their contribution to GuestXR.

A multidisciplinary team of professionals working together to ensure social harmony in Virtual and Augmented Reality environments

The GuestXR consortium is coordinated by the Eurecat technology centre together with the University of Barcelona and it is made up of eight organisations from six countries.

GuestXR multidisciplinary team includes professionals with backgrounds in extended reality, machine learning, Artificial Intelligence, social psychology, the neuroscience of emotions, multisensory integration, research ethics and technology transfer.

4 universities, 2 research centers, 2 companies

Eurecat

About

Eurecat is the leading Technology Centre of Catalonia, providing the industrial and business sector with differential technology and advanced expertise.

The centre offers solutions to their innovation needs and boosts their competitiveness in a fast-paced environment. It brings together the expertise of 650 professionals who generate a volume of income of 50M€ per year. Serving more than a thousand companies, Eurecat is involved in 200 projects of R&D national and international with high strategic value.

Contribution to GuestXR

Eurecat is in charge of coordinating the project through the Multimedia Technologies Unit. With large expertise in areas such as physics, mathematics, computer science, acoustics, audio processing and musicology, Eurecat takes responsibility of the auditory aspects of GuestXR. In addition, the centre will manage the project's communication and dissemination activities and is responsible for the launch of an Open Call for projects and artistic residencies.

Virtual Body Works (VBW)

About

Virtual Bodyworks S.L (VBW) specialises in immersive virtual reality focused on medical and psychological rehabilitation.

The primary expertise of VBW is immersive virtual reality, interaction, and evaluation of immersive systems. VBW carries out research and applications in the area of virtual embodiment. This is the substitution in immersive virtual reality of participants' bodies by life-sized virtual bodies.

Contribution to GuestXR

VBW will be responsible for the overall architecture of the GuestXR platform. Also, it will be in charge multiple possible representations of the Guest and its actions in the virtual environment AR or VR. Finally, VBW will investigate representation through embodiment in AR, its effectiveness and its impact of representations of remote participants.

Interdisciplinary Center (IDC) Herzliya

About

Reichman University (AKA IDC Herzliya) was declared Israel's first private university in August 2021, with a broad range of undergraduate and graduate programs, including PhD programs. Our interdisciplinary research is recognized world-wide in both competitive grants and publications. We have over 150 tenure-track researchers across 9 schools with more than 30 research centers, labs and institutes, working on over 100 active grants.

Contribution to GuestXR

Two separate groups in RUNI are involved in the project. The Advanced Reality Lab (PI: Prof Doron Friedman) is in charge of designing and developing the deep reinforcement learning algorithms behind the Guest. The Brain lab/institute will use behavioral and neuroimaging methods (fMRI) to investigate the principles and neural underpinnings of multisensory integration in rich virtual environments compared to simpler laboratory conditions. Our research will also be aimed at increasing the accessibility of VR/AR technologies to hearing and visually impaired individuals (including deaf and blind).

Maastricht University (UM)

About

Maastricht University (UM) is the most international university in the Netherlands, with more than half of the student population and almost half of the academic staff coming from abroad. Together, they represent more than

100 different nationalities. The university distinguishes itself with its innovative education model, international character and multidisciplinary approach to research and education.

UM houses the Brain and Emotion Laboratory within the Faculty of Psychology and Neuroscience. The Lab has significant experience in neuroscientific and psychological research on emotional bodily expression, as well as the neural underpinnings of bodily perception.

The Science and Technology Studies research group (MUSTS) at The Faculty of Arts and Social Sciences has experience connecting academic knowledge and expertise in data science with societal needs, exploring themes related to the socially responsible application of digital technologies.

Contribution to GuestXR

UM takes primary responsibility for two key parts of the GuestXR project. UM will lead the psychological and neuroscientific investigation of social interaction and group dynamics, focusing primarily on body language. The university will also coordinate the implementation of an "Ethics-by-Design" methodology, which will be used throughout the project, in order to ensure that ethics are a key consideration in all aspects of GuestXR.

Inria

About

Inria is the French national research institute for digital science and technology. In 200 project teams, most of which are shared with major research universities, more than 3,900 researchers and engineers explore new paths, often in an interdisciplinary manner and in collaboration with industrial partners to meet ambitious challenges. As a technological institute, Inria supports the diversity of innovation pathways: from open source software publishing to the creation of technological startups.

Contribution to GuestXR

Inria is in charge of coordinating the design and evaluation of multi-sensory displays involved in the project. Inria will more specifically conceive haptic technologies, and will also participate in the development of several use cases.

Uniwersytet Warszawski

About

The research in GuestXR will be carried out by the team of the Robert Zajonc Institute for Social Studies (ISS) University of Warsaw, especially by the Center for Complex Systems and New Technologies. ISS is an interdisciplinary research-oriented institution grouping sociologists, psychologists, economists, and political scientists. The main objective of the institute are to monitor social, political and economic processes of societies in transition and to promote interdisciplinary approach in studying these processes. The ISS is a national member of the Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research. The ICPSR is the world's largest institution (developed in the US) collecting data from all sociological, economic and political investigations and protecting high quality standards of data collection and processing. It provides its members with unlimited access to these data. Robert Zajonc Institute for Social studies is a curator of many longitudinal social surveys studies including all the polish waives of World Values Survey, International Social Survey, Social Diagnosis, European Social Survey.

Center for Complex Systems and New Technologies at ISS is primarily responsible for conducting the research in GuestXR specializes in applying complexity approach and new technologies to understand social and behavioural processes and phenomena. The researchers associated with the Center come from different backgrounds including social psychology, computer science, physics, biology, and cognitive science. The Center has experience with applying social science knowledge to understand social aspects of new technologies and to address problems and enhance opportunities created by new technologies.

Contribution to GuestXR

UW will work with UM on the psychological and neuroscientific investigation of social interaction and group dynamics. An important task involves the design and implementation of the simulations of social processes occurring in VR, where the simulations will be the base for the pre-learning phase of deep learning algorithms. UW will work with Reichman University in designing the GuestXT. UW is also involved in use cases, where it is primarily responsible for the climate change usecase.

g.tec medical engineering GmbH (GTEC)

About

g.tec medical engineering GmbH (GTEC) is a thriving Austrian SME with about 35 employees. GTEC makes and sells hardware, software, and complete systems to collect and analyse EEG from people. GTEC is also active in several current collaborative funded projects and has successfully completed over 20 such projects. GTEC was founded in 2004 and has had the same main technical proficiencies since its foundation: design, manufacturing, testing and certification of tools to collect and analyse human biosignals.

Contribution to GuestXR

GTEC will work on social and affective modelling for GuestXR, where we will develop an electrophysiology training environment that allows recording different biosignals to distinguish and classify affective categories. We will also contribute to the project's communication and dissemination activities.

Universitat de Barcelona

About

UNIVERSITAT DE
BARCELONA

eventLAB
Neuroscience
& Technology

applications in psychology and neuroscience.

The University of Barcelona is the top Spanish university in scientific production, and the main university research centre in Spain and at the European level. The Institute of Neurosciences of the University is interdisciplinary including research groups in includes research groups in neurobiology, neuropharmacology, pathophysiology, neurology, psychiatry, clinical psychology, neuropsychobiology and cognitive neurosciences. The research will take place in the Event Lab (Experimental Virtual Environments for Neuroscience and Technology) which is part of the Institute and which specialises in virtual reality and its

Contribution to GuestXR

The research of the Event Lab is concentrated around effective virtual human characters to represent people in virtual reality, and also on conflict resolution. The Event Lab PI Mel Slater is scientific leader of the project.

CONSORTIUM

A multidisciplinary team of professionals working together to ensure social harmony in Virtual and Augmented Reality environments

The GuestXR consortium is coordinated by the Eurecat technology centre together with the University of Barcelona and it is made up of eight organisations from six countries.

GuestXR multidisciplinary team includes professionals with backgrounds in extended reality, machine learning, Artificial Intelligence, social psychology, the neuroscience of emotions, multisensory integration, research ethics and technology transfer.

4

Universities

2

Companies

2

Research centers

<p>Advanced Reality Lab – Interdisciplinary Center (IDC) Herzliya Read more</p>		
<p>Uniwersytet Warszawski Read more</p>		
<p>Universitat de Barcelona – Event Lab Read more</p>		

Figure 22: View of consortium page <https://questxr.eu/consortium/>

COORDINATOR

Eurecat

Eurecat is the leading Technology Centre of Catalonia, providing the industrial and business sector with differential technology and advanced expertise.

The centre offers solutions to their innovation needs and boosts their competitiveness in a fast-paced environment. It brings together the expertise of 650 professionals who generate a volume of income of 50M€ per year. Serving more than a thousand companies, Eurecat is involved in 200 projects of R&D national and international with high strategic value.

Contribution to GuestXR

Eurecat is in charge of coordinating the project through the Multimedia Technologies Unit. With large expertise in areas such as physics, mathematics, computer science, acoustics, audio processing and musicology, Eurecat takes responsibility of the auditory aspects of GuestXR. In addition, the centre will manage the project's communication and dissemination activities and is responsible for the launch of an Open Call for projects and artistic residencies.

Figure 23: Example of partners' page

2.1.2.4 Use cases

GuestXR Validation System

The GuestXR machine learning system is to be validated in four use cases

4 use cases

GuestXR machine learning system will be initially tested in situations which may generate conflict, or interactions involving participants with communication problems or in contexts that trigger debate such as climate change.

Validating The Guest potential

Success will be measured both by the outcomes of lab-based experimental studies and through the live deployment of the system by trusted organisations that are members of the GuestXR User Group, and the resulting performance data.

Use cases

Make participants aware

Virtual game to examine the extent to which participants, supervised by The Guest, might experiment attitudes and behavioural change towards climate change after a direct experience with consequences of making cooperative vs. competitive decisions in the tragedy of commons applied to global warming.

Conflict resolution

Validation of The Guest in geopolitical conflict resolution in conjunction with organisations like the United Nations. This use case will aim to bring members of two sides together for acquaintance and building mutual trust, and them, shifting their attitudes from competitive orientations to cooperative orientation for a final conflict mediation.

Social application for hearing impaired

This use case aims to promote the social inclusion of the hearing-impaired individuals in VR and AR, as well as boosting the abilities of healthy individuals to communicate efficiently with individuals with hearing loss, by combining voice analysis tools, multisensory devices and displays with multisensory training protocols and interfaces.

Innovative experiments

Use case selected from the public Open Call, considering proposals for the facilitation of new VR experiences, inclusivity, and promoting learning and creativity.

User group call

Do you want to have early access to our case studies?

GuestXR's user group is composed of a broad group of stakeholders, including multinational agencies, representatives of the arts, multinational companies, academia and civil society groups, which contribute providing feedback and support to the project consortium.

BUTTON - Join our user group!

GUESTXR SYSTEM VALIDATION

The GuestXR machine learning system is to be validated in four use cases

4 use cases

GuestXR machine learning system will be tested in social situations that may generate conflict, during interactions involving participants with communication problems or in contexts that trigger debate, such as climate change.

Validating The Guest potential

Success will be measured both by the outcomes of lab-based experimental studies and through the live deployment of the system by trusted organisations that are members of the GuestXR User Group, and the resulting performance data.

Make participants aware

Virtual game to examine the extent to which participants, supervised by The Guest, might experiment attitudes and behavioural change towards climate change after a direct experience with consequences of making cooperative vs. competitive decisions in the tragedy of commons applied to global warming.

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Innovative experiments

Use case selected from the public Open Call, considering proposals for the facilitation of new VR experiences, inclusivity, and promoting learning and creativity.

USER GROUP

Do you want to have early access to our use-case studies?

GuestXR's user group is composed of a broad group of stakeholders, including multinational agencies, representatives of the arts, multinational companies, academia and civil society groups, which contribute providing feedback and support to the project consortium.

Join our user group!

Figure 24: GuestXR website use cases page - <https://questxr.eu/use-cases/>

2.1.2.5 User group

GuestXR's user group is composed of a broad group of stakeholders, including multinational agencies, representatives of the arts, multinational companies, academia and civil society groups, which contribute to provide feedback and support to the project consortium.

User group members will have early access to GuestXR solution and applications.

info@guestxr.eu

Click to subscribe to our newsletter

Do you want to take part?

FORM TO JOIN THE USER GROUP

USER GROUP

Join us!

GuestXR user group

GuestXR's user group is composed of a broad group of stakeholders, including multinational agencies, representatives of the arts, multinational companies, academia and civil society groups, which contribute to provide feedback and support to the project consortium.

User group members will have early access to GuestXR solution and applications.

 info@guestxr.eu

 Click to subscribe to our newsletter

Do you want to take part?

Name

Email

Subject

Message

I have read and I accept the [privacy information](#).

Figure 25. View of GuestXR user group page - <https://guestxr.eu/user-group/>

2.1.2.6 News & Events

This page will show articles on GuestXR project advances and results, as well as general assembly meetings.

It will also include an agenda announcing events where GuestXR consortium is organising or attending/participating (conferences, meetings, fairs, congresses and workshops) and a list of articles regarding the events attended, type of dissemination activity, target-profile/audience covered, number of attendees and an overview of the feedback received.

Within this page project events such as the final conference, webinars and workshops will be announced and promoted. Each event will count with a specific page with the information on the event, agenda and form to register. After the event, the presentations and documents delivered during the event will be made available for download through the page, as well as video recording of the sessions.

NEWS & EVENTS

Find here GuestXR updates!

Agenda

More events coming soon!

Project news & events

Adapting VR environment into 3D restaurant for a newspaper interview

February 22, 2022

Adapting VR environment into 3D restaurant for a newspaper interview GuestXR project researchers from the Event Lab of the University of Barcelona developed a 3D Virtual Reality restaurant environment for a Financial Times newspaper interview. The environment is based on "VR United", a VR technology created by Drs Ramon Oliva, Alejandro Beacco, and Jaime Gallego...

[Read more](#)

Recent Posts

Adapting VR environment into 3D restaurant for a newspaper interview
February 22, 2022

GuestXR project kicks-off! January 27, 2022

Tweets by @GuestXR

GuestXR Retweeted

Mel Slater
@meislater

I would like to thank @PicoInteractive for their fantastic help in supporting our @ERC_Research project #MoTIVE and the Horizon Europe project @GuestXR! <https://twitter.com/meislater/status/1492842954796449795>

Feb 22, 2022

GuestXR Retweeted

TRACTION
@TRACTION_EU

Can #accessibility be applied in #VirtualReality ?@TransmediaCat are using #EyeTracking technology to understand how to best position #subtitles

[Embed](#)

[View on Twitter](#)

Figure 26. View of GuestXR news & events page - <https://guestxr.eu/news-events/>

2.1.2.7 Resources

This page will gather all public materials of the project, including visual materials, videos, public deliverables, scientific publications and media features. Specific pages for each type of content will be created depending on the number of results for a correct visualisation. At M2, the page references the expected results and materials to be included.

Main outcomes

- **Deliverables:** All public reports will be published on this website for in-depth access to project outputs.
- **Promotional materials:** Project promotional materials produced (rollups, posters, infosheets, etc.).
- **Scientific publications:** All scientific publications related to the project's research in open access journals or as conference proceedings.

- **Audiovisual materials:** A set of short videos will be produced to present key GuestXR concept and applications.
- **Media impacts:** Main articles featuring the GuestXR project in generalistic and specialised media outlets.

MAIN OUTCOMES

GuestXR public materials

- ✓ **Deliverables**
All public reports will be published on this website for in-depth access to project outputs.
- ✓ **Promotional materials**
Project promotional materials produced (rollups, posters, infosheets, etc.).
- ✓ **Scientific publications**
All scientific publications related to the project's research in open access journals or as conference proceedings.
- ✓ **Audiovisual materials**
A set of short videos will be produced to present key GuestXR concepts and applications.
- ✓ **Media impacts**
Main articles featuring the GuestXR project in generalistic and specialised media outlets.

Figure 27. View of GuestXR resources page

2.1.2.8 Contact

This section shows a form for visitors to send comments and questions. The form includes the fields (Name, Surname, Email, Company, Phone, Subject and Message).

On the other hand, the email info@guestxr.eu has been created and is shown at the website as another way of contact. The project coordinator has access to that email in order to manage all information requests received.

GET IN TOUCH!

Contact us via the form below

About GuestXR

GuestXR is an EISMEA-funded project developing an immersive online social space based on Extended Reality through a Machine Learning agent as the medium to facilitate social interaction.

Coordinator information

Aurora Sesé

Eurecat Technology Centre
Project Coordinator

Mel Slater

Universitat de Barcelona
Scientific coordinator

 info@guestxr.eu

 [Click to subscribe to our newsletter](#)

Ask us!

Name

Email

Subject

Message

I have read and I accept the [privacy information](#).

Figure 28. View of GuestXR contact page

2.1.3 Imagery

To illustrate the project website, partners have considered the recommendations of the project [“Better Images of AI”](#), aiming at creating a collection of better stock photos for AI and providing tips on which images to use, avoiding stereotyped images on the technology, as well as the use of images laden with historical assumptions about gender, ethnicity and religion.

Taking into consideration this project advice, all images used for GuestXR website try to:

- Represent a wider range of humans and human cultures than a ‘Caucasian businessperson’ or ‘humanoid robot’
- Represent the human, social and environmental impacts of AI systems
- Reflect the realistically messy, complex, repetitive and statistical nature of AI systems
- Accurately reflect the capabilities of the technology: generally applied to specific tasks and are not of human-level intelligence
- Show realistic applications of AI
- Avoid monolithic or unknowable representations of AI systems
- Avoid using electronic representations of human brains, or robots

The images used from the website were obtained from project partners libraries in order to represent the project concepts. EUT also made use of partners images and pictures retrieved from free-to-use image banks.

2.1.4 Header and footer layout

The GuestXR website's menu is available from all pages, allowing visitors to find the information that they are interested in no matter how they reached the site.

The overall design and home page of the website includes the following elements:

Figure 29: Header and footer layout

Figure 30: GuestXR footer

Figure 31: GuestXR header

2.1.5 Management and updating policy

The website has been developed by Eurecat with the inputs received from all partners in the consortium.

The GuestXR website will be updated with new content and information every time a new dissemination action is done, a result is achieved or there is other news worth publishing.

2.1.6 Analytics

GuestXR website has installed Matomo in the platform's back end to monitoring all the traffic and obtain, periodically, reports about the site's performance. Instead of Google Analytics, Matomo does not compromise data security and privacy, guaranteeing full data ownership and that none of it is ever sent to other services and third parties.

Figure 32: View of Matomo dashboard

2.1.7 Site hosting, installation and maintenance

Eurecat has been responsible for setting up the website (domain purchase, hosting and Wordpress.org configuration), as well as creating content and design the fixed sections.

On the other hand, Eurecat will be responsible for maintaining the site until the project's end adding content and updating it regularly. All pages have been optimised for the search engines (SEO), ensuring that the GuestXR website is well positioned in the browsers. The website will be maintained three years after the projects' end.

2.1.8 Data protection

GuestXR website is compliant with all European requirements and standards with regards to data protection and observes the GDPR. See the legal warning, cookies policy and privacy policy on Annex.

The website has been adapted to the latest directives published by the Spanish Data Protection Agency (AEPD) in July 2020, which came into force on October 31st, 2020 with the purpose to align the cookies installation with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) consent requirements. The latest version of the AEPD “*Guidelines on the Use of Cookies*”, compared with the previous one, specifies that the consent must be granted by clearly accepting the cookies or carrying out similar actions to click “I accept”. In that sense, browsing the website or the use the scroll bar cannot be construed as an affirmative action, nor the use of cookie walls that do not provide an alternative to the consent.

In order to comply with the new AEPD directives, EUT, as the owner of the website www.guestxr.eu, has installed a cookies banner allowing the user to decide on which non-necessary cookies to install. By complying with the novel regulation, web analytics will only be tracked for users accepting this type of cookies, which may result in losing some statistics on the number of web visits, page viewed or number of users.

The users may revise their cookies’ selection at any time as the Cookies Setting Banner is available at the bottom right part of the page. The website also includes specific pages for allocating the privacy policy (<https://guestxr.eu/privacy-policy/>), the cookies policy (<https://guestxr.eu/cookies-policy/>) and the legal warning (<https://guestxr.eu/legal-warning/>).

The webpage includes two forms gathering personal data from users: a **contact form to manage user’s queries** and an **external sign-up form for users to subscribe to GuestXR newsletter**. For both forms EUT is the data controller. The data of the contact form will be transferred to partners involved in the project to better reply the requests, while the users’ data of the community of interest will not be disclosed to third-parties and will be processed by Mailchimp.

The website will also include specific forms to manage the registration of interest users to project events. The data included in these forms will be disclosed with the organising partner with the solely objective to register the users to the event and be able, afterwards, to send event materials to attendees.

2.1.9 Website KPIs

The following table introduces an initial set of GuesXR Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for assessing the website performance. Progress until the end of the project will be reported in the interim progress reports.

As we expect to not be able to record all website analytics due to the new AEPD regulation on third-party cookies, such the ones used for getting analytics on website performance (see *more information on section 7. Data Protection*), KPIs related to the website activity have been designed and established with caution taking the regulation into account.

Table 1: Website KPIs

Strategy	Indicator	Means of verification	Target by the end of the project
Website	Number of web visits	Matomo Analytics	>2.000 annually*
	Number Pages Viewed		>2.000 annually*
	Number page / session		>1.0
	Number users		>500 annually*
	Avg. session time		>1.00 min

*in average

3 ANNEXES

3.1 Website privacy policy

Who is the Data Controller of your personal data?

Data Controller: FUNDACIÓ EURECAT (“Eurecat” or “Data Controller”)

Tax Identification Code: G-66210345

Address: Avda. Universitat Autònoma 23, 08290 Cerdanyola del Vallès, Barcelona (Spain)

Email address: legal@eurecat.org

Telephone: +34 93 238 14 00

Data Protections Officer’s email address: dpo@eurecat.org

What are the purposes and the legal basis for the processing of your personal data?

The Data Controller shall process your identifying and contact data (name, surname, email address...) as the data included at your query, given through the contact form, for the purpose to manage and answer the user contact. The legal basis for its data processing is to develop the proper actions to answer the user’s contact (art 6.1 b) GDPR).

The Data Controller shall process your identifying and contact data (name, surname, email address...) as the data included at your query, given through the “User Group” contact form, for the purpose to manage and answer the user contact as well as to inform or access at the GuestXR Group. The legal basis for its data processing is to develop the proper actions to answer the user’s contact (art 6.1 b) GDPR).

The Data Controller shall process your identifying and contact data (name, surname, email address...), for the purpose of give access to your data access to the GuestXR consortium partners, you may consult the detailed lit at [Consortium](#), in those cases that should be strictly necessary to manage properly the web form purposes. The legal basis for its data processing is the legitimate interest as well as the proper actions to execute the data purposes (art 6.1 b) and f) GDPR). You may obtain further information regarding the recipients of your data consulting “*Who are the recipients of your data?*” section at this Privacy Policy.

The Data Controller shall process your identifying and contact data (name, surname, email address...), for the purpose of subscribe and send GuestXR project information, as well as Eurecat’s general information, (both newsletters or solely the selected by the user). The legal basis for its data processing is the consent granted by the user (art 6.1 a) GDPR).

The Data Controller shall process data related your preferences (postal code, interests, preferences, professional information) given though the web forms, for the purpose profiling the user to sending the Newsletter segmented with contents that are aligned with the user interests. The legal basis for its data processing is the consent granted by the user (art 6.1 a) GDPR).

The Data Controller shall process and have access to user’s navigation data (IP, location, browser...) because of the accessories cookies installed and agreed, for the purpose of improve the Web services and contents, further information regarding cookies data processing’s, consulting the [Cookies Policy](#). The legal basis for its data processing is the consent granted by the user (art 6.1 a) GDPR).

Who are the recipients of your data?

Eurecat is the main recipient of your data, however, they may be accessible to third parties that develop services to the Data Controller. When access to the user's data is required for the services developed, it shall be submitted and fulfill with the legal obligations, which are those of article 28 GDPR'S. In any event, the services providers shall not process the user's data for their own or different purposes and shall not overreach from the services purposes, and, in any case, shall not rent, sold, or make it available to third parties.

The Data Controller shall not transfer your data to third parties without your prior consent, which should fulfill the legal requirements.

The Data Controller may transfer your data to third parties in case of legal obligations to do so, without the user consent.

The personal data obtained by the web forms may be revealed to certain consortium partners whit whom Eurecat cooperate, for the purpose to manage and answer the user contact, as well as to execute the proper actions to carry out the web form purposes for which the data was given. This data access by the consortium partners, does not entail a data assignment for its own purposes. You may consult the detailed list of the project consortium partner [here](#).

How long will your data be kept?

Eurecat shall process your data as long as is necessary to the purposes of the processing which the data were disclosed for and, in any case, until you ask its deletion.

Even if the User ask the deletion of the data, the Data Controller shall keep them blocked for the term required to afford legal obligations or make them available to third parties with the proper capacities because of legal issues.

Is your data subject to international data transfers?

Your data shall not be subjected to international data transfer, it means outside the European Economic Area ("EEA"). However, Eurecat may have services suppliers located or whom develop its services out of the EEA, in these sense, the Data Controller shall ensure to the User that their data object to international transfers shall be protected with the legal measures, that may consist on standard contractual clauses or privacy certifications, bot legal measures approved by the European Union.

Is your data subjected to profiling or automated decisions?

Your data shall not be subjected to automated decisions because of Eurecat's data processing's.

The Data Controller shall process your data for profiling purposes in case of you have consent the newsletter subscription where you have completed the optional web form parts related to your interests. Its profiling shall be done with the solely purpose of segment each newsletter to those subject matters that according to your profile may interest you and to avoid you the reception of all the newsletter activity. The profiling actions solely shall be done in case of you have given your consent to the Newsletter subscription, and the users profiling do not be used in other different ways or purposes.

Eurecat through the accessory cookies installed and agreed by the user, may process user's navigation data to profiling for the purposes of improve the Web services and contents, to obtain navigation and Web statistics, to develop and implement Web improvements. The cookies profiling is subjected to the cookies installed which are strictly linked to the user consent. You may consult further cookies information consulting the [Cookies Policy](#).

What are your personal data rights?

Current privacy laws granted several rights to the users regarding the processing of their data, main information about them is detailed herein:

1. **Right of access:** users are entitled to find out which of your personal data are processed and the processing purposes
2. **Right of rectification:** users are entitled to request the rectifications regarding their data at any time
3. **Right of erasure:** users are entitled to request, at any time, that their data shall be erased from the data controller storage. However, as set out in the above section related on data storage, in certain circumstances to compliance with the laws in force may prevent this right from being exercised
4. **Right to object:** users are entitled to object to their personal data from being processed in relation to any of each purposes processing's, pursuant to the privacy policies that may apply in each case.
5. **Right to restriction of processing:** users are entitled to request the restriction of purposes processing's in the following cases:
 1. If considers that their data are incorrect or inexact;
 2. If considers that their data has been processing with not the proper legal basis and considered to restrict the processing's instead of requests its erasures;
 3. If the data recorded are no longer required for the processing purposes which were collected for but need its storage to file a lawful claim;
 4. If the user having exercised its right to object for a specific purpose, is awaiting a reply from the data controller to this regard
6. **Right to data portability:** user is entitled to request that their personal data that were submitted to the data controller are being disclosed to another data controller, only in case that its request is technically possible and reasonable to do so.

How may you exercise your data rights?

Notwithstanding that your data has been collected within your consent or the proper legal basis, you may object to the data processing at any time whereby without consequences for you, however, depending on the right exercised certain services shall not be able to be rendered.

The users may exercise their rights according to the law terms and conditions by addressing to Eurecat through either of the following:

(i). by email address to legal@eurecat.org

(ii). by postal to Parc Tecnològic del Vallès. Avda. Universitat Autònoma 23, 08290 Cerdanyola del Vallès (BCN)

The user may have the right to contact to the Data Controller Data Protection Officer by email to dpo@eurecat.org

User, if considers that their data shall not been processed with legal basis or its requests or rights shall not been attended properly by the Data Controller, are entitled to file a claim upon the Supervisory Authority competent on data protection matters, it is the Agencia Española de Protección de Datos (www.aepd.es).

3.2 Website legal warning

By fulfilling the Spanish Information Society Services and Electronic Commerce Act 34/2002 of 11th July (LSSICE), users are hereby informed that the domain owner www.guestxr.eu is FUNDACIÓ EURECAT (hereinafter “**Provider**” or “**Eurecat**”), whose identification data details are as follows:

Registered Office: Av. Universitat Autònoma 23, 08290 Cerdanyola del Vallès, Barcelona (Spain)

Tax Identification Code: G66210345

Email address: info@guestxr.eu

Register details: registered at the Foundations Registry of the Generalitat de Catalunya with the number 2826

SUBJECT MATTER AND SCOPE

The main purpose of the Legal Notice is to provide the information regarding access and uses to the web www.guestxr.eu (hereinafter “**Web**”) which has the subject matter of provide inform about the GuestXR project as well as to allows to the Internet users access thereto.

By accessing and/or using the Web, are considered to hold the role of a user (hereinafter “**Users**”) an in consequence the acceptance with no reservations of each and whole parts of its Legal Notice, Privacy and Cookies policies or, any other terms and conditions linked to the Web.

Users must carefully read the Legal Notice, the Privacy and Cookies Policy, also to consulting its content often to stay tuned about it because of the Eurecat’s right to carry out improves or updates at the Web contents or services, without prior notice being necessary. The Users who do not accept the content of its Legal Notices, Privacy or Cookies Policy or any related terms and conditions related to the Web, Eurecat begs you to not access neither to use the Web.

TERMS OF USE

Users are the sole responsible for the use they could make of the Web as for the content reproduce out or through the Web and for the damages that it may cause. The Provider shall not be held liable for any damage from the Users Web access and uses. Users shall be held liable for any damages that the Provider could be caused as a result of a breach of the obligations undertaken by virtue of this Legal Notice, the Privacy and Cookies Policy and the applicable regulations.

Users undertake to carefully use the whole Web, its contents and services, fulfilling to the applicable regulations, the rules of moral generally accepted, good conduct and public order as well as this Legal Notice and any other legal conditions or obligations included on the Web.

Users undertake to refrain the Web use, the contents and services thereto, for illegal or prohibited purposes, that could harm rights and interests of third parties or infringe this Legal Notice, as well as any actions that could damage, disable, overload, harm or hinder the normal use of the Web and its contents and services to other users.

Moreover, User expressly undertakes to do not delete, manipulate, disturb disable or from any other way damage the data, software and hardware, technical resources, electronic documents on the Web, as not to hinder access by other users to the Web by massive use of he Web resources, within those Eurecat provide the Web services and contents, and any other actions could damage, interrupt or leading errors on the Web.

Likewise, Users undertake not to introduce programs, viruses, macros applets, controllers ActiveX or any other logical or sequential characters devices that may cause any kind of alteration on the Provider or third parties' systems.

Users agrees that the documents, graphics published on the Web server may include technical incorrections or typographic errors, as well as the Provider or its services suppliers, may develop Web improvements and/or changes at any time without it entitled the User to claim for damages.

In the same way, Users agrees that Eurecat reserves' the right at any time to modify or interrupt the Web, conforming to "Modifications and Interruptions", as well as the right to disable, limited or blocked Web access that infringes the Legal Notice, the third party's rights, the applicable laws and/or public order, without it entitled the User to claim for damages against the Provider.

INTELLECTUAL OR INDUSTRIAL PROPERTY RIGHTS

The Provider or its licensors are the holders of all the intellectual or industrial property rights related to the Web and the contents thereto, this being deemed to mean, in particular but not limited to, the designs, data bases, underlying programs (includes source an object codes), as well as different elements included on the Web (texts, logos, graphics, photographs, colors...), structure, order and the legal texts (hereinafter "**Contents**"). The trademarks and trade names (hereinafter "**Distinctive Signs**") are owned by the Provider or the licensors.

The Web use by the User does not grant him intellectual and industrial property rights licenses. Likewise, reproducing, copying, distributing, putting available to third parties or making public communications, transforming or modifying the Contents and/or the Distinctive Signs, by the User is prohibited unless express consent to do so has given from who concern or are lawful actions.

MODIFICATIONS AND INTERRUPTIONS

Access to the Web and its contents and services thereto, may be interrupted due to maintenance tasks or failures beyond the Provider which may be solved by the period required.

Eurecat hereby reserves the right to making modifications at any time without User notifications related to the Web, contents, services, scope, and any information or resources thereto.

Likewise, Provider reserves the right to disable or blocked the Web access or delete or limited the contents in case that considers that infringes this Legal Notice, third parties' rights, the applicable laws and/or the public order.

Provider is not liable about the security mistakes also to the damages that may cause at Users devices (hardware and software) and for the files or documents therein storage, as a consequence of the viruses, Internet or telephone companies' failures, interferences, disconnects or omissions from the operative functions of the Web and/or because of reasons that not belongs to Eurecat.

Provider is not liable from the direct or indirect damages because of Web use, from the server and its modifications and/or interruptions that may be caused to the User or third parties'.

LINKS POLICY (LINKING WEB AND LINKED WEB)

1. a) Linking Web

Thirds parties whom intent to include link to this Web (hereinafter "**Linkikng Web**") must fulfil the laws in force and may not host inappropriate, illegal pornographic, violent, etc content.

Under no circumstances whatsoever shall the Provides be held liable for the contents from Linking Web nor does promote, guarantee, monitor or recommends the contents thereof.

If the Linking Website does not comply with any of the aforementioned terms, it must be deleted immediately.

1. b) Linked Web

This Web may include links to webs that belongs to third parties (hereinafter “**Linked Web**”) which are allowed to User’s access. However, the Provider shall not be held responsible for the contents from Linked Web instead Users will be the responsible for accepting and checking the access to it time by time.

The Linked Web and its respective links do not imply Provider approval and support, neither to the existence of any marketing or business relationship between the Provider and the third parties located on Linked Web.

SOCIAL MEDIA

Provider may have social media profiles in several social media networks, which accessible to the Users though the links included on the Web, as well as join directly through the social media platform.

The social media networks have their own terms and conditions of use and its privacy policies, for this reason, Users who follows the Provider profile on a social media, shall be under the legal terms stablished therein, as a consequence of that, Provider shall not be liable for any Users damages.

In accordance with the aforementioned, the User data belongs to the social media network, except for those cases that the data has been collected within marketing actions (contest, lottery, promotion...) promoted by the Provider.

The Provider may delete Users comments on their own social media profile in case that considers that infringes this Legal Notice, third parties ‘rights, the applicable laws and/or public order. In addition, Provider shall be held from liability because of the inappropriate use on its social media profiles by the User as well as the publications that dimmish third parties’ rights, against applicable regulations, public order or for made a profit from Provider social media networks contents and quotes.

Hereby the links to the privacy policies from the social networks on which the Provider may have an active profile:

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/es/privacy>

Facebook: <https://ca-es.facebook.com/privacy/explanation>

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/intl/es/yt/about/policies/#community-guidelines>

LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/legal/privacy-policy? l=es_ES

APPLICABLE LAW

This Legal Notice and Web shall be governed and interpreted according to Spanish law.

Any disputes that may arise because of the Web use shall be submitted to the relevant Courts and Tribunals in accordance with the consumers regulations applicable.

CONTACT

User may query or comment regarding the Legal Notice or any other matter related to the Web as well as contact to the Provider, though this email address info@guestxr.eu

3.3 Website cookies policy

WHAT ARE COOKIES AND WHY DO WE USE THEM ON THE WEBSITE?

A cookie is a file that is downloaded to the user's device when they access certain websites which stores and retrieves information about the browsing activity on their computer.

Cookies allow this website, among other things, to store and retrieve information about the user's decisions and habits. The cookies that exist on this website are necessary for it to function.

It is important to highlight that the use of cookies does not provide access to the user's personal data.

WHAT TYPE OF COOKIES EXIST?

Depending on the time they remain active, Cookies can be divided into session or persistent cookies.

- **Session cookies** are designed to collect and store data while the user accesses a website and are removed as soon the explorer is closed. They are normally used to store information which only needs to be kept in order to provide the service requested by the user on just one occasion.
- **Persistent cookies** remain stored on the device and can be accessed and handled during a period specified by the user of the cookie, which may be from a few minutes to several years.

Additionally, depending on the organisation managing them, cookies may be classified as first-party or third-party cookies.

- **First-party cookies** are sent to the user's device from a computer or domain managed by the website publisher and are used to provide the service requested by the user.
- **Third-party cookies** are sent to the user's device from a computer or domain that is not managed by the website publisher, but by another organisation that handles data obtained from the cookies. Additionally, depending on the organisation managing them, cookies may be classified as first-party or third-party cookies.

In terms of their purpose, the types of cookies are:

- **Technical cookies:** Technical cookies allow the user to browse a website, platform or application and use the different service options found there.
- **Profiling cookies:** Profiling cookies allow the user to access the service with some predefined general features based on a series of criteria on the user's device such as language, settings, etc.
- **Analytical cookies:** Analytical cookies allow the website owner to track and analyse user behaviour on the websites to which they are linked. The information collected is used to measure activity on the websites and to create users' browsing profiles, with the aim of introducing improvements.
- **Advertising cookies:** Advertising cookies allow the advertising spaces which the publisher puts on the website to be managed as efficiently as possible.

WHAT TYPE OF COOKIES DOES THE WEBSITE USE?

The user may be consult and set up the website cookies managed by the website publisher at Cookie settings.

The user should take account that although the cookies may be set up, certain cookies are needed and must be installed to ensure the proper access and use of the website, this cookies does not require the user's agreed neither its management.

COOKIE	TYPE	DURATION	DESCRIPTION
_pk_id.1.a126	persistent	1 year 27 days	This cookie is set by the web analytics service Piwik. In order to comply with privacy regulations the analytics service does not track personal data, for example we anonymize your IP address.
_pk_ses.1.a126	persistent	30 minutes	This cookie name is associated with the Piwik open source web analytics platform. It is used to help website owners track visitor behaviour and measure site performance. It is a pattern type cookie, where the prefix _pk_ses is followed by a short series of numbers and letters, which is believed to be a reference code for the domain setting the cookie.
CONSENT		16 years 4 months 15 hours	These cookies are set via embedded youtube-videos. They register anonymous statistical data on for example how many times the video is displayed and what settings are used for

			<p>playback.No sensitive data is collected unless you log in to your google account, in that case your choices are linked with your account, for example if you click "like" on a video.</p>
cookielaawinfo-checkbox-advertisement		1 year	<p>The cookie is set by GDPR cookie consent to record the user consent for the cookies in the category "Advertisement".</p>
cookielaawinfo-checkbox-analytics	0	11 months	<p>This cookie is set by GDPR Cookie Consent plugin. The cookie is used to store the user consent for the cookies in the category "Analytics".</p>
cookielaawinfo-checkbox-functional	0	11 months	<p>The cookie is set by GDPR cookie consent to record the user consent for the cookies in the category "Functional".</p>
cookielaawinfo-checkbox-necessary	0	11 months	<p>This cookie is set by GDPR Cookie Consent plugin. The cookies is used to store the user consent for the cookies in the category "Necessary".</p>
cookielaawinfo-checkbox-others	0	11 months	<p>This cookie is set by GDPR Cookie Consent plugin. The cookie is used to store the</p>

			user consent for the cookies in the category "Other.
cookieLawinfo-checkbox-performance	0	11 months	This cookie is set by GDPR Cookie Consent plugin. The cookie is used to store the user consent for the cookies in the category "Performance".
elementor		never	This cookie is used by the website's WordPress theme. It allows the website owner to implement or change the website's content in real-time.
googtrans	session	session	This cookie stores the translation preference: it contains translation languages and expires when you close your browser
IDE		1 year 24 days	Used by Google DoubleClick and stores information about how the user uses the website and any other advertisement before visiting the website. This is used to present users with ads that are relevant to them according to the user profile.

test_cookie		15 minutes	This cookie is set by doubleclick.net. The purpose of the cookie is to determine if the user's browser supports cookies.
viewed_cookie_policy	0	11 months	The cookie is set by the GDPR Cookie Consent plugin and is used to store whether or not user has consented to the use of cookies. It does not store any personal data.
VISITOR_INFO1_LIVE		5 months 27 days	This cookie is set by Youtube. Used to track the information of the embedded YouTube videos on a website.
YSC		session	This cookies is set by Youtube and is used to track the views of embedded videos.
yt-remote-connected-devices		never	These cookies are set via embedded youtube-videos.
yt-remote-device-id		never	These cookies are set via embedded youtube-videos.
yt.innertube::nextId		never	These cookies are set via embedded youtube-videos.
yt.innertube::requests		never	These cookies are set via embedded youtube-videos.

HOW DO YOU DISABLE COOKIES IN A BROWSER?

The user can adjust the settings in their browser so as not to accept the use of cookies, in which case the user would not have a customized browsing experience. Choosing this setting may result in certain parts of the website not being accessible, as this may cause less effective browsing.

Most browsers currently allow the user to choose whether they want to accept cookies and which types. These settings are usually found in the “settings” or “preferences” in your browser’s menu.

Depending of the browser used by the user and its functionalities used may suppose the installation of cookies that are considered ad a Third-party cookies. For example, if the user chooses Google’s browser and use its option of translate full website, Google install cookies in the user’s computers that are not managed by the website publisher. The settings of the browser cookies should be done by the user directly at the browser website.

These are the instructions to change the cookie settings in the main browsers:

- Information about cookies for [Mozilla Firefox](#).
- Information about cookies for [Internet Explorer](#)
- Information about cookies for [Opera](#).
- Information about cookies for [Google Chrome](#).
- Information about cookies for [Safari](#)

3.4 Community of interest privacy policy

Data Controller: The Data Controller is Fundació Eurecat, with Vat number G66210345 sited at Av. Universitat Autònoma 23, 08290, Cerdanyola del Vallès (BCN), legal@eurecat.org Data Protection Officer contact information de contact dpo@eurecat.org (the “Data Controller”)

Purposes of the data treatment: identifying and contact data (name, surname, email address) shall be processed to submitting you information related the checkbox selected, as well as to profiling you to segment the newsletter activity to your interests.

Legal Basis: The legal basis for processing your data is the consent granted (art 6.1 a) GDPR).

Recipients: The data shall not be ceded to third parties; however, the data may be accessible to the project consortium partners as well as to third parties as to the Data Controller services providers or, because of legal obligations. Further information about it at [Privacy Policy](#).

Storage: The data shall be stored for the term required to develop the purpose of the treatment, or, until the data subject request its deletion.

Automated decisions and profiling: the data shall not be object to automated decision, however your data shall be subjected to profiling actions to select and send solely the newsletter that includes such information that may interest you.

Rights: the consent may be revoked at any time. You may also have the right to access, rectify, erase the data and exercise your right to restriction of the processing data and to ask for the portability of the data according to the legal conditions contacting the data controller at: **Fundació Eurecat** a Av. Universitat Autònoma 23, 08290 Cerdanyola del Vallès (Barcelona), or, by email a legal@eurecat.org

Supervisory Authority: in case the user shall not obtained the execution of a right petition, or its the response or, shall be considered it unsatisfactory, or require further information about the subject’s data rights, you may consult to the Agencia Española de Protección de Datos (www.agpd.es).

Further Information: you may consult further information about the data treatment at [Privacy Policy](#).

3.5 Contact form privacy policy

Data Controller: The Data Controller is Fundació Eurecat, with Vat number G66210345 sited at Av. Universitat Autònoma 23, 08290, Cerdanyola del Vallès (BCN), legal@eurecat.org Data Protection Officer contact information de contact dpo@eurecat.org (the “Data Controller”)

Purposes of the data treatment: identifying and contact data (name, surname, email address) and the information included at your query shall be processed to answering your contact.

Legal Basis: the legal basis for processing your data are the proper actions to respond to your contact (art 6.1 b) GDPR).

Recipients: The data shall not be ceded to third parties; however, the data may be accessible to the project consortium partners as well as to third parties as to the Data Controller services providers or, because of legal obligations. Further information about it at [Privacy Policy](#).

Storage: The data shall be stored for the term required to develop the purpose of the treatment, or, until the data subject request its deletion.

Automated decisions and profiling: the data shall not be object of profiling neither automated decision.

Rights: the consent may be revoked at any time. You may also have the right to access, rectify, erase the data and exercise your right to restriction of the processing data and to ask for the portability of the data according to the legal conditions contacting the data controller at: **Fundació Eurecat** a Av. Universitat Autònoma 23, 08290 Cerdanyola del Vallès (Barcelona), or, by email a legal@eurecat.org

Supervisory Authority: in case the user shall not obtained the execution of a right petition, or its the response or, shall be considered it unsatisfactory, or require further information about the subject’s data rights, you may consult to the Agencia Española de Protección de Datos (www.agpd.es).

Further Information: you may consult further information about the data treatment at [Privacy Policy](#).

3.6 User group privacy policy

Data Controller: The Data Controller is Fundació Eurecat, with Vat number G66210345 sited at Av. Universitat Autònoma 23, 08290, Cerdanyola del Vallès (BCN), legal@eurecat.org Data Protection Officer contact information de contact dpo@eurecat.org (the “Data Controller”)

Purposes of the data treatment: identifying and contact data (name, surname, email address) and the information included at your query shall be processed to answering your contact.

Legal Basis: the legal basis for processing your data are the proper actions to manage your access to the GuestXr Group, as well as to inform you and answer your questions related de GuestXr User Group and how to join in. The legal basis are the legitimate interest as the proper actions to manage the form purposes (art 6.1 b) and f) GDPR).

Recipients: The data shall not be ceded to third parties; however, the data may be accessible to the consortium partners as well as to third parties as to the Data Controller services providers or, because of legal obligations. Further information about it at [Privacy Policy](#).

Storage: The data shall be stored for the term required to develop the purpose of the treatment, or, until the data subject request its deletion.

Automated decisions and profiling: the data shall not be object of profiling neither automated decision.

Rights: the consent may be revoked at any time. You may also have the right to access, rectify, erase the data and exercise your right to restriction of the processing data and to ask for the portability of the data according to the legal conditions contacting the data controller at: **Fundació Eurecat** a Av. Universitat Autònoma 23, 08290 Cerdanyola del Vallès (Barcelona), or, by email a legal@eurecat.org

Supervisory Authority: in case the user shall not obtained the execution of a right petition, or its the response or, shall be considered it unsatisfactory, or require further information about the subject's data rights, you may consult to the Agencia Española de Protección de Datos (www.agpd.es).

Further Information: you may consult further information about the data treatment at [Privacy Policy](#).